

TRIBOLOGICAL STUDIES OF FRICTION ON JOURNAL BEARINGS

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ABSTRACT: It is a known fact that connecting rod is the important intermediate member between the piston and the Crankshaft. Its primary function is to transmit the push and pull from the piston pin to the crank pin, thus converting the reciprocating motion of the piston into rotary motion of the crank. Existing Bearing of connecting rod is manufactured by using non ferrous materials like Gunmetal, Phosphor Bronze etc.. This paper describes the tribological behavior analysis for the conventional materials i.e. Brass and Gunmetal as well as New non metallic material Cast Nylon. Friction and Wear are the most important parameters to decide the performance of any bearing. In this paper attempt is made to check major tribological parameters for three material and try to suggest better new material compared to conventional existing material. It could help us to minimize the problem of handling materials like Lead , Tin, Zinc etc.After Test on wear machine we found that Cast Nylon compared to Brass and Gunmetal for the same operating and lubricating condition, have less value of coefficient of friction which help us to minimize power lost due to friction and assist in increasing overall engine efficiency of the engine.

KEY WORDS: Tribology, Friction, Wear, Cast Nylon, Artificial cooling, engine efficiency

1. Introduction

Friction always occur at machine parts which run together. This affects the efficiency of machines negatively. Today, many industrial applications use vacuum conditions. Therefore, it became essential to determine the tribological behavior of the machine components running under these conditions. In this paper, friction and wear behavior of BRONZE and BRASS alloy which is used commonly in the industry as a bearing material. Nowadays, especially with the growth of the plastics industry and the development of high-strength fibers, vast range combinations of materials are available for use in engineering fields. To take the advantages of new material developed, in this paper attempt is made to offer Cast Nylon 6 as the non metallic material in place of conventional material.

Journal bearing materials are expected to have several properties such as low friction coefficient, high load capacity, high heat conductivity, compatibility, high wear and corrosion resistance. These properties directly affect the fatigue and wear life of the bearing [1].

. The researchers investigate friction and wear behavior of materials[2] because of the adverse effect observed in the performance and life of machinery components. Much of the research reported in the literature was carried out under the atmospheric conditions. However, some tribological behaviors have been recently investigated under the vacuum conditions. Especially, as a result of some new

developments in aeronautic, space, electronic, material, metallurgy, chemistry, coating and manufacturing industrial areas necessitate the machinery components to be investigated under the different conditions. Therefore there is great interest among the researcher to estimate to the effect of the loads and speeds on the material's friction and wear behavior.

In the past few years, wood, iron and skin have been used as journal bearing materials. Later, brass, bronze and white metal have also found some applications. Currently, in addition to these bearing materials, aluminum and zinc based materials are used as journal bearing materials. With technological improvements, self-lubricated sintered bearings and plastic materials are used where continuous lubricating is impossible. Therefore, it is essential that the bearing material be chosen depending upon area of application. Copper based materials are widely used as bearing materials because they have high thermal and electrical conductivity, self-lubrication property, good corrosion and wear resistance [3]. Friction and wear properties of these materials can be improved by adding tin [5] Tin bronze (90% Cu and 10% Sn) is the most suitable bearing material under corrosive conditions, at high temperatures and high loads.[4]

Lead and tin based white metal alloys are used due to their antifriction property as bearing materials. These alloys are produced by casting and spray deposition method. These casting alloys contain inter metallic phase. The process variables during spray forming of

Babbitt bearing metal alloy strongly influence the microstructure and porosity of the spray deposits. Wear and wear mechanisms depend on a lot of factors at journal bearings. These factors and their effects can be examined in a tribological system. These factors include base friction element, opposite friction element, interim matter, ecology, loading and movement [5]. Of these wear mechanisms, adhesion wear is affected by pressure and velocity concerning load and movement. This p.v. value (load capacity) is important for wear analysis. If bearings are used appropriately on p.v. values, wear quantity can be decreased [6].

The modeling of friction and wear is an important engineering problem. In the process of design of machine elements and tools operating in contact conditions, engineers need to know areas of contact, contact stresses, and they need to predict wear of rubbing elements. Friction, wear and contact problems are subjects of numerous experimental and theoretical studies. [7]

2. Experiment setup and procedure

In this study, the bearing materials like BRONZE, BRASS, and CAST NYLON 6 which are widely used in industry were investigated in order to see the possible effects of friction.[8]. The diameter and the length of the pins were 10 mm and 30 mm respectively. Before the experiments, the top surfaces of each pins were finished with abrasive paper so that they had the same surface conditions with the abrasive disk surface (surface roughness 0,35µm).All three pins are shown in the figure-1.In the figure first pin is made from Gun metal. Second is made from Cast Nylon and last is made from the Brass.

Figure 1 Three different investigated pins

OBJECTIVE OF EXPERIMENTS: Experimental set up is shown in Figure 2.

1. To Study the frictional behavior of the selected materials and the effect of various speeds, loads and time on wear.
2. To study the relationship between coefficient of friction, frictional force, speed and load.
3. To find the effect of lubricant on wear rate and coefficient of friction.

Figure 2 Experimental complete setup

Materials were procured from the market and sample of 100 mm. dia. And 25 mm. long pins were prepared for each type of materials. Three different materials (Brass, Bronze and Cast Nylon) are selected. Readings were recorded on every 10 seconds and time span for each set up was 90 minutes. In this study, friction coefficient, temperature values and wear losses of bearing samples are determined by wearing on radial journal bearing. All three materials were tested with the identical lubricating condition i.e. during the test SAE40 oils were utilized[9]

3. Result and discussion

The tests on the adhesion wear using friction coefficient has been done on three different material specimens and its average values are given in Table(1).With the help of software and arrangement made[10].,It was possible to record reading on every 10 seconds and for the 60 Minutes test readings were recorded for the

Table(1).A

Material : Gun Metal Duration 60 Minutes Oil : SAE40

S r.	Lo ad N	Spe eds rpm	Coeff. Of friction	Temper ature Centigr ade	Wear (Micro n)	Rem arks
1	30	650	0.1755 03054	34.650 91159	0.1755 0305	Aver age
2	50	850	0.0171 79584	40.254 82415	0.0380 5515	Aver age
3	70	1000	0.0813 18852	41.138 54613	0.0813 1885	Aver age

Table(1).B

Material : Nylon Duration 60 Minutes Oil : SAE40

S r.	Lo ad N	Spe eds rpm	Coeff. Of friction	Temper ature Centigr ade	Wear (Micro n)	Rem arks
1	30	650	0.0483 03300	33.053 81529	0.0483 0330	Aver age
2	50	850	0.0649 44286	39.537 70003	0.0288 6508	Aver age
3	70	1000	0.0288 65088	40.160 87564	0.0288 6508	Aver age

Table(1).C

Material : Brass Duration 60 Minutes Oil : SAE40

S r.	Lo ad N	Spe eds rpm	Coeff. Of friction	Temper ature Centigr ade	Wear (Micro n)	Rem arks
1	30	650	0.2596 27300	37.562 19655	0.2597 01089	Aver age
2	50	850	0.0347 53453	41.448 05233	0.0676 22157	Aver age
3	70	1000	0.1262 44546	42.465 27455	0.1262 44546	Aver age

The entire testing was divided in three phases. The details of all three phases are mentioned below:

First Phase : 650 rpm , load 30 N and duration 60 minutes

Second Phase : 850 rpm , load 50 N and duration 60 minutes

Third phase : 1000 rpm , load 70 N and duration 60 minutes

4. Conclusions

1. The test is carried out for the Brass, Gun metal and New material named Cast Nylon was to check existing materials and new material tribological behavior. 2. While analyzing the available data it is found that the Cast Nylon is lighter in weight and heaving low co-efficient of friction and good wear and chemical resistance. At present Brass and Gun Metal both are utilized for the manufacturing of Bush Bearing of small end connecting rod. Both metals are quite heavy compared to Cast Nylon (Table 1). If we can replace existing material by lighter weight

material like Cast Nylon, the overall engine performance can be improved. We know that the power lost due to friction can be find out by using equation ($P = \mu V W$).

(3) At highest speeds i.e. 1000 rpm, referring Table 1 the coefficient of friction of Gun Metal is Four Times higher and Coefficient of friction of Brass is Six times more compared to Cast Nylon coefficient of friction at 1000 rpm. Here we have taken same lubricating oil SAE 30 for all three materials. Hence if we replace conventional Bushing of small end connecting rod by new material Cast Nylon and we can reduce power lost due to friction and increased over all efficiency of the engine. .

(3) At 1000 rpm and 70 Newton load, the temperature induced is 42.46 0C in Brass, Gunmetal 41.12 0C and Cast Nylon 40.16 0C. Because of less temperature for Cast Nylon, the requirement of artificial cooling would be reduced and it would increase bearing life.

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